

Synthesis of Paracrystalline Diamond

Hu Tang¹, Xiaohong Yuan¹, Yong Cheng², Hongzhan Fei³, Fuyang Liu¹, Tao Liang¹, Zhidan Zeng¹, Takayuki Ishii³, Ming-Sheng Wang², Tomoo Katsura³, Howard Sheng^{4,*}, Huiyang Gou^{1,5,*}

¹Center for High Pressure Science and Technology Advanced Research, Beijing 100094, China

²State Key Laboratory of Physical Chemistry of Solid Surfaces, College of Materials, Xiamen University, Xiamen, Fujian 361005, China

³Bayerisches Geoinstitut, Universität Bayreuth, Bayreuth D95440, Germany

⁴Department of Physics and Astronomy, George Mason University, Fairfax 22030, USA

⁵College of Environmental and Chemical Engineering, Yanshan University, Qinhuangdao 066004, Hebei, China

*Corresponding authors: Howard Sheng (hsheng@gmu.edu), Huiyang Gou (huiyang.gou@hpstar.ac.cn)

Solids in nature can be generally classified into crystalline and non-crystalline states¹⁻⁷, depending on whether long-range lattice periodicity is present in the material. The differentiation of the two states, however, could face fundamental challenges if the degree of long-range order in crystals is significantly reduced. Here we report a paracrystalline state of diamond that is distinct from either crystalline or amorphous diamond⁸⁻¹⁰. The paracrystalline diamond reported in this work, consisting of sub-nanometer-sized paracrystallites that possess a well-defined crystalline medium-range order up to a few atomic shells^{4,5,11-13}, was synthesized in high-pressure high-temperature conditions (e.g., 30 GPa, 1600 K) employing fcc-C₆₀ as a precursor. The structural characteristics of the paracrystalline diamond were identified through a combination of X-ray diffraction, high-resolution transmission microscopy, and advanced molecular dynamics simulation. The formation of paracrystalline diamond is a result of densely distributed nucleation sites developed in compressed C₆₀ as well as pronounced second-nearest-neighbor short-range order in amorphous diamond due to strong *sp*³ bonding. The discovery of paracrystalline diamond adds an unusual diamond form to the enriched carbon family¹⁴⁻¹⁶, which exhibits distinguishing physical properties and can be furthered exploited to develop new materials. Furthermore, this work reveals the missing link in the length-scale between amorphous and crystalline states across the structural landscape, which has profound implications for recognizing complex structures arising from amorphous materials.

Amorphous solids refer to materials that do not possess long-range periodicity as exhibited in crystals¹⁻¹¹. Consequently, Bragg peaks associated with crystalline arrangements of atoms are absent or obscured in the diffraction signals of amorphous materials, which renders the recognition of their structural organizations notoriously difficult. Due to decades of research effort, it is now understood that structural ordering on the atomic level of amorphous solids is ubiquitous, as manifested by the short-to-medium-range ordering in metallic glasses⁵⁻⁷ and the continuous-random networks (CRN) of amorphous semiconductors¹⁻³. Moving from the short range into the extended length-scale abutting the long-range scale, however, our understanding of the structural arrangements remains much more limited, and it is often complicated by capricious crystalline structural ordering encountered in amorphous materials^{13,17-19}. In an attempt to resolve this structural enigma, a paracrystalline structure model was proposed^{11,19}, in which nanosized paracrystallites were introduced to the amorphous matrix to account for the crystalline medium range order (MRO). A crucial question to answer is, in the configurational space, are we able to identify a state of matter that is fully packed with tiny paracrystals possessing only MRO but devoid of long-range order (LRO)? The identification of such a material state is essential to obtaining much-needed structural information differentiating amorphous solids with and without crystalline MRO. This material state with dominating crystalline MRO would serve as the Rosetta stone to uncover the nature of a large set of non-crystalline materials. In this work, we report the discovery of such a substance in diamond, termed paracrystalline diamond (p-D).

Among myriads of carbon allotropes, diamond stands out as an important industrial material, featuring complete sp^3 bonding. Diamond exists in many crystal forms, among which the most familiar are cubic diamond (CD) and hexagonal diamond (HD). However, unlike other fourfold-coordinated systems such as Si and Ge, synthesis of fully sp^3 -bonded amorphous carbon, or amorphous diamond (a-D), has proven difficult. Chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and physical sputtering methods, approaches for forming amorphous Si (a-Si) or Ge (a-Ge), only result in diamond-like carbon (DLC) with variable sp^3 fractions²⁰. Not until recently was Zeng *et al.* able to synthesize recoverable a-D by means of laser heating in a diamond-anvil cell (DAC)⁹. Structure-wise, the as-obtained a-D can be described by the CRN model, in line with other tetrahedral amorphous systems. It was also reported that a-D can be produced by shock compression involving highly nonequilibrium high-pressure and high-temperature (HP-HT) conditions⁸.

The current realization of a-D requires relatively high pressure (40-55 GPa) and a rapid cooling rate (10^6 - 10^{10} K/s)^{8,9}, and the finite sample size (several tens of μm) inevitably hampers our understanding of the structure, properties, and synthesis mechanism. As such, synthesizing large and high-quality a-D remains both highly demanding and technically challenging. In this study, we attempted to synthesize mm-sized non-crystalline diamond using a large-volume

multi-anvil press (MAP). Conventional MAP technology could not generate such ultrahigh pressures in a mm-sized sample. However, our recently developed ultrahigh-pressure technique using MAP is capable of generating pressures to 50 GPa in mm-sized samples²¹. Using this technique, we succeeded in synthesizing p-D with a 1.0 mm diameter at a pressure of 30 GPa. We present details regarding the synthesis and structural analyses of this sample and articulate the synthesis mechanism below.

We selected zero-dimensional fullerene (C_{60}) in a fcc crystal to monitor its phase evolution at 30 GPa and a temperature range of 1200-1800 K. Previous investigations have demonstrated that C_{60} can only transform into polymerized C_{60} crystals and disordered sp^2 - sp^3 carbon under HP-HT (13-25 GPa)²²⁻²⁶. Here, at an elevated pressure condition of 30 GPa, the X-ray diffraction patterns (XRD) of the recovered samples synthesized at various temperatures are shown in Fig. 1a and Extended Data Fig. 1a. The diffraction signals are distinctly different from the initial fcc- C_{60} (Fig. 1b), signaling the formation of new phases. Broadened diffraction peaks around ~ 2.9 , ~ 5.4 , and $\sim 8.4 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ are reminiscent of amorphous materials, bearing considerable resemblance to those of a-D⁹ and DLC carbon with high-fraction sp^3 bonds²⁴. Moreover, the recovered samples heated above 1400 K are highly transparent (e.g., Fig. 1a inset), suggesting a dense diamond-like (sp^3 -dominated) structure. To quantitatively examine the composition of sp^2 vs. sp^3 in the samples, we utilized Raman and electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS)^{27,28}. Raman and EELS characterizations (Figs. 1c-d and Extended Data Fig. 1) indicate that the sample recovered from 1400 K contains a residual amount ($\sim 5.2\%$) of sp^2 bonds, whereas samples above 1400 K are completely sp^3 -bonded, demonstrating successful synthesis of non-crystalline diamond at a pressure much lower than previously reported^{8,9}. The densities of the samples at 1500 and 1600 K are estimated to be 3.20 and 3.25 g/cm^3 (Extended Data Fig. 1), respectively, close to that of amorphous diamond (3.30 g/cm^3)^{8,9}. Further increasing the temperature to 1800 K leads to temperature-induced crystallization (Extended Data Fig. 1a).

High-resolution transmission microscopy (HRTEM) images of the recovered samples are shown in Fig. 2 and Extended Data Fig. 2 respectively. Lattice fringes associated with LRO are not found in the HRTEM images, indicating the disordered nature of the samples beyond a certain length ($\sim 1 \text{ nm}$). We randomly selected small regions ($7.0 \times 7.0 \text{ nm}^2$) and conducted fast Fourier transformation (FFT) to obtain the scattering signals in the momentum space. The diffuse halos of the FFT patterns corresponding to the selected areas confirm the overall amorphous feature, consistent with the XRD results. On a finer scale, however, visual inspections indicate that the images become more ordered for samples synthesized at elevated temperatures, which is also evidenced by the narrowing FFT rings with increasing temperature. The ordered HRTEM images resemble those of a-Si films and bulk metallic glasses (BMGs) with MRO structures^{17,29,30}, but they differ from the previously reported a-D described with the

CRN model⁹. For the samples annealed at 1400-1600 K, a considerable amount of ordered clusters within 0.5-1.0 nm are visible in the HRTEM images. Within the spatial distance of ~ 1.0 nm, two types of lattice fringes are identifiable, which are found to be close to the atomic arrangements along the $[1\bar{1}0]$ and $[010]$ zone-axes of cubic and hexagonal diamonds (CD and HD), respectively, as shown in Fig. 2f. This finding is further validated by the FFT patterns of the selection areas ($2.0 \times 2.0 \text{ nm}^2$), where the intensified “diffraction” spots matching CD or HD crystalline order are recognizable. Note that both cubic and hexagonal MRO clusters are highly distorted because the inclusive angles ($72.1 \pm 1.5^\circ$ for cubic and $89.5 \pm 2.5^\circ$ for hexagonal) of the lattice fringes deviate from those of pristine CD (70.3°) and HD (90°) crystals³¹. The observed morphology of the as-synthesized non-crystalline diamond is clearly distinguished from a-D, hinting at the formation of crystalline MRO structures dominating the samples.

To uncover the hidden structural ordering in the obtained non-crystalline diamond, we relied on large-scale classical molecular dynamics (MD) simulation³² employing a recently developed realistic angular-dependent potential for carbon³³ and adiabatic-bias MD³⁴ to accelerate dynamics. Starting from fcc-C₆₀ and mimicking the experimental HP-HT conditions (e.g., 1600 K and 30 GPa), we revealed how the fullerene evolves into the non-crystalline diamond deterministically. Upon the formation of nearly complete sp^3 bonding at 1600 K, small but prolific clusters with CD- and HD-like atomic packing gradually take form. These MRO clusters typically encompass 4-5 atomic shells, henceforth referred to as paracrystallites. With prolonged simulation time, the amount of paracrystallites increases and eventually saturates at a volume fraction of $\phi = 0.7$, which is rationalized to be the maximum paracrystal content attainable in the given simulation condition due to thermodynamic constraints. Above a certain threshold (e.g., $\phi = 0.3$), the paracrystallites start to interconnect and percolate, which is a distinguishing feature of the material.

Structural differences of non-crystalline materials are identified by the structure factor $S(Q)$. Subtle but definite differences in $S(Q)$ (e.g., a-D vs. p-D) can be experimentally discriminated for closely related structures. In our simulation, we accurately determined $S(Q)$ from the atomistic models based on the Ornstein-Zernike equation³⁵. The comparison of the simulated $S(Q)$ of a-D and p-D ($\phi = 0.7$) is provided in Fig. 3a. While both $S(Q)$ profiles are characteristic of non-crystalline materials, the differences are conspicuous, evidenced by peak intensity variations. For a-D, the intensity of the first main diffraction peak at ($\sim 2.9 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$) is lower than that of the second peak at ($\sim 5.4 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$). In comparison to a-D, as the volume fraction of paracrystallites increases, the intensity of the first peak monotonically rises, accompanied by a decrease in the intensity of the second peak (Extended Data Fig. 3a). The intensity ratio of the first peak to the second peak I_1/I_2 is positively correlated to the degree of MRO arrested in the sample. This relationship is thus used to estimate the content of paracrystallites in the experimental samples. Indeed, the extracted $S(Q)$ of the synthesized samples from the XRDs³⁶

in Fig. 1 exhibits exactly the same predictive trend (Fig. 3b). Plotting I_1/I_2 against paracrystal volume fraction ϕ , we find that high proportions of paracrystallites exist in the samples above 1400 K (Fig. 3c). For instance, the amount of paracrystallites reaches as high as 47% and 52% for samples at 1500 and 1600 K, similar to those (46% and 48%) obtained from HRTEM images using autocorrelation function (ACF) analysis¹⁷. A satisfactory match between the $S(Q)$ of a paracrystalline model ($\phi = 0.5$) and that of the 1500 K sample is achieved. Figure 3d presents the structural model of a homogeneous p-D with 70% CD- and HD-like paracrystallites (~ 0.8 - 1.0 nm in size) and remaining 30% amorphous diamond. The simulated HRTEM image of this atomistic model (Fig. 3d) is in striking agreement with the experimental ones, validating the paracrystalline nature of the samples at 1500 and 1600 K.

To further distinguish the structural difference between a-D and p-D and enable identification of CD- or HD-like atomic packing in p-D, we employed the common-neighbor analysis (CNA)³⁷ and orientational order analysis (OOA) methods³⁸. Figure 4a illustrates the atomic structures of p-D and a-D visualized based on their respective degree of MRO. Through CNA, high fractions of CD and HD-like clusters are found to be abundant in p-D, but they are starkly absent in a-D. Moreover, the corresponding atomic structure of p-D visualized by the orientational order parameter \bar{q}_6 ³⁸ reveals the orientational order of the local clusters, supporting the presence of MRO clusters in p-D. To shed light on the size of the paracrystallites, we adopted an orientational correlation function (OCF) $\kappa(r)$ (defined in Methods). Fig. 4b shows the radial distribution functions (RDFs) $g(r)$ and the orientational correlation functions of p-D and a-D, respectively. Both a-D and p-D have nearly the same $g(r)$ profile for the first peak, in agreement with their respective tetrahedral atomic environments. However, the intensity of the first peak in the $\kappa(r)$ of a-D is significantly lower than that of p-D where just two peaks are visible in the profile, suggesting that a-D has short-range ordering (SRO) within two coordination shells. In contrast, the first five sharp peaks in p-D indicate the strong MRO and the subsequent three peaks are weakened and broadened because of the absence of LRO. Previously, nano-polycrystalline diamond (NPD) with ultrafine grains has been synthesized from various sp^2 carbons including C_{60} under HP-HT conditions³⁹⁻⁴³. Our simulations of NPD with different grain sizes (1.20-2.40 nm) reveal a completely different morphology in NPD due to the presence of LRO (Extended Data Fig. 3). The paracrystallites in p-D are found to be severely distorted in comparison to perfect diamond lattices of which the level of distortion is on par with the grain-boundary atoms of ultrafine NPD (Extended Data Figs. 3c and 4d). This accounts for the absence of Bragg diffraction peaks from its XRD pattern.

We attribute the formation of p-D to two main factors (see Methods). First, we discovered that the CRN-type a-D exhibits strong diamond-like SRO in the first-two atomic shells (16 atoms), in comparison to that of a-Si (Extended Data Figs. 4 and 5). This is consistent with the argument that sp^3 carbon has the largest tetrahedral parameter among all group IV elements⁴⁴. The

pronounced intrinsic diamond-like SRO of a-D greatly facilitates the development of MRO, and consequently the formation of diamond paracrystallites. Second, the successful synthesis of p-D depends highly on the structure of the C₆₀ precursor. We argue that the formation of p-D is a result of a nucleation-controlled process, where the formation of orientationally correlated *sp*³ bonds between neighboring C₆₀ units offers fertile sites for nucleation. Our simulated results (see Methods and Extended Data Figs. 6-10 for details) demonstrate that the formation of p-D goes through three main stages: (i) inter-buckyball bond connection (15% *sp*³ bonds) during compression to 30 GPa at room temperature; (ii) kinetically controlled polymerization and collapse of buckyballs during heating to 1600 K at 30 GPa; and (iii) the formation of p-D from a-D during isothermal annealing at 1600 K and 30 GPa. In particular, the *sp*³ bonds formed in the early stage of polymerization are orientationally ordered in the local contact regions (Extended Data Fig. 6), which persists into the a-D state at high temperatures and contributes to the formation of p-D. Abundant and homogeneous *sp*³ bonding of C₆₀ by polymerization under high pressure and low temperature prevents the otherwise heterogeneous nucleation and growth of crystals, allowing the formation of p-D in a divide-and-conquer manner. To further understand the critical role of C₆₀ in the formation of p-D, we examined other *sp*²-dominated carbons in experiments (carbon onion and type-1 glassy carbon) as a precursor in the same HP-HT conditions, which failed to synthesize p-D in our experiments (Extended Data Fig. 1a). We surmise that the bundled single-wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) with well-aligned carbon bonds may provide abundant *sp*³ bonding sites through intermolecular polymerization under high pressure⁴⁵, like in C₆₀, allowing for the synthesis of p-D.

The unique MRO structures of p-D elicit new physical properties. The mechanical properties of p-D were assessed by the measurements of Vickers' and nanoindentation hardness. p-D exhibits highly isotropic Vickers hardness *H_v* of 116.1±3.6 GPa and nanoindentation hardness *H_N* of 102.1±1.4 GPa (Extended Data Fig. 11), comparable with natural diamond⁴². The obtained Young's modulus *E* (937.2±10.1 GPa), shear modulus *G* (437.9±4.7 GPa), and bulk modulus *K* (363.3±3.9 GPa) of p-D are close to those of diamond (1140 GPa, 535 GPa, and 443 GPa)⁴⁶, consistent with our *ab initio* predictions (Extended Data Fig. 11e), making it an appealing candidate for ultra-hard materials. Moreover, a measurement of thermostability of p-D in the air (Extended Data Fig. 12) gives an onset oxidation temperature of 950 K, much higher than those (673-873 K) of DLC films⁴⁷, nano diamond⁴⁸, CVD diamond⁴⁹ and NPD. These outstanding combinations of mechanical properties and oxidation resistance endow p-D with great potential for niche technological applications. Lastly, we shall point out that the paracrystalline state diamond may exist in other forms, for example, with different types and compositions of paracrystallites contingent upon the starting material and synthesis conditions, awaiting to be explored to obtain novel carbon materials with unusual properties.

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Author contributions H. G. and H. S. proposed and supervised the project; H. T., H. F., T. I., and T. K. synthesized the samples; H. T., X. Y., Y. C., F. L., and M. S. W. performed the structure characterizations; H. T., X. Y., T. L., and Z. Z. measured the properties; H. S. performed the theoretical calculations; H. T., H. S., and H. G. analyzed data and wrote the manuscript with the contributions of all authors.

Competing interests The authors declare no competing interests.

Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to H. S. or H. G.

Methods

Sample synthesis

The starting material, C₆₀, was purchased from Alfa Aesar. HP-HT experiments were performed using an ultrahigh-pressure MAP⁵⁰ at Bayerisches Geoinstitut of University of Bayreuth in Germany and Center for High Pressure Science & Technology Advanced Research (HPSTAR) in China. The synthetic pressure was set to 30 GPa, implemented using carbide anvils with 3-mm truncation and 7-mm MgO + 5 wt.% Cr₂O₃ octahedron. The temperature range was from

1200 to 1800 K, generated using a LaCrO₃ heater. The pressure was calibrated at 2300 K by evaluating the Al₂O₃ content in bridgmanite⁵¹, and the temperature was monitored using a type-D thermocouple. The starting material was pre-compressed into Pt capsules with diameter of 0.8 and 1.2 mm and height of 1.6 mm at a pressure of 200 MPa. The samples were compressed to 30 GPa in 7 h at room temperature and heated to the designated temperatures within a heating rate of 100 K/s. *In situ* Raman (532 nm) of C₆₀ under high pressure was conducted without pressure transmitting medium by using a symmetrical DAC with a culet size of 300 μm. The samples and ruby spheres for pressure calibration were loaded into the DAC sample chamber with 120 μm in diameter with a pre-indented rhenium gasket.

Structure characterizations

To collect high-quality XRD data, the powder mode of Bruker D8 Venture diffractometer equipped with a Mo K α radiation was employed. The samples were fixed on an organic XRD holder and rotated 720° in total within an acquisition time of 10 min. A background file was obtained with an empty organic holder with the same collection condition. To extract the structure factors from the XRD data, we followed the optimization method proposed in Ref. 36. The microscopic structures of the samples were characterized by the FEI Talos-F200s transmission electron microscope (TEM) operated with an accelerating voltage of 200 keV. The bonding analysis of the samples was done by using Raman and (EELS. The Raman spectra were acquired with two different wavelengths (325 nm and 532 nm) of laser excitation by using a Renishaw-type micro-Raman spectroscopy system. The EELS data were obtained using the ARM-200F (JEOL Ltd.) microscope equipped with a spherical aberration corrector (CEOS GmbH).

Properties measurements

The Vickers hardness H_v and fracture toughness K_{IC} was measured using a micro-Vickers hardness tester (Q10A⁺, Qness GmbH, Austria) with a Vickers diamond indenter at 4.9 and 9.8 N for a holding time of 15 s. H_v and K_{IC} were determined from the equations⁴² as:

$$H_v = \frac{1854.4F}{L^2} \quad (1)$$

$$K_{IC} = \frac{0.016(E/H_v)^{0.5}F}{C^{1.5}} \quad (2)$$

where F (N) is the applied load, L (μm) is the arithmetic mean of the two diagonals of the Vickers indentation, C (μm) is the average length of the radial cracks and E is Young's modulus of p-D.

The nanoindentation hardness (H_N) was measured with a three-sided pyramidal Berkovich diamond indenter (Keysight Nano Indenter G200), and the samples were loaded to the maximum load of 50 mN at a loading rate of 2 mN/s with a holding time of 10 s. The Young's modulus (E) was derived from the loading/unloading-displacement curves according to the

Oliver-Pharr method⁵². The values of Vickers hardness, nanoindentation hardness, and Young's modulus (E) are given as an average value taken from more than 5 tests. The nanoindentation data of p-D was calibrated with natural diamond (100) surface.

The thermostability was evaluated using a thermogravimeter and differential scanning calorimeter, NETZSCHSTA 449 C, from room temperature to 1773 K in the air with a heating rate of 5 K/min.

Computational methods

Structural model of a-D

In this work, a-D was obtained by conducting extensive *ab initio* molecular dynamic (AIMD) simulations, following the protocol introduced in our previous work⁹. In order to yield better statistics, our simulation system was enlarged to 500 carbon atoms. AIMD was performed with the density functional theory-based Vienna Ab-initio Simulation Package (VASP)⁵³. The projector augmented wave potential (PAW)⁵⁴ with a valence configuration of $2s2p$ and the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) were used in the simulation. The kinetic energy cutoff was set to 400 eV, and the simulation was conducted on the gamma point only. In brief, liquid carbon was slowly quenched from 5000 to 300 K in a NPT (constant number of atoms, pressure and temperature) ensemble under a hydrostatic pressure condition of 50 GPa. The cooling rate was 2.5×10^{13} K/s. A phase transition during the quench process leads to the formation of a-D. The as-obtained high-pressure a-D structure was gradually relaxed to ambient pressure using a conjugate-gradient geometric optimization method. To cross-check the structure resulting from *ab initio* modeling, a different route was employed to generate a-D. In this approach, we applied the bond-switching algorithm⁵⁵, also known as the WWW method, to generate ideal CRN configurations with different sizes employing the Keating interatomic potential⁵⁶. The 500-atom CRN structure was further subjected to simulated annealing via *ab initio* MD to minimize local stresses and to achieve a more realistic structural model.

Structural model of p-D and phase transition from C₆₀ to p-D under HP-HT

Both classical MD³² and *ab initio* MD simulations were carried out to study the structure evolution of C₆₀ under HP-HT conditions and simulate the formation of p-D. For classical MD, a newly developed angular-dependent interatomic potential (C-ADP)^{33,57} was used to describe carbon. The development of the realistic C-ADP potential was based on mapping the complex energy landscape obtained with density-functional-theory-based calculations of more than 5000 atomic configurations of C ($>10^6$ atoms in the fitting database)^{58,59}. The empirical potential has been tested to be reliable in describing carbon phase behaviors over a wide temperature and pressure range (0-100 GPa) without compromising the computational speed, enabling us to simulate large samples across an extended temporal scale (in the sub-

microsecond regime). The detailed MD simulation steps are given as follows:

- 1) A 36000-atom fcc-C₆₀ crystal was created with C₆₀ buckyballs randomly oriented. The fcc-C₆₀ crystal was equilibrated at 300 K and zero pressure for 1 ns.
- 2) The well-equilibrated C₆₀ crystal was compressed to 30 GPa at room temperature at a constant compression rate of 0.5 GPa/ns.
- 3) The system was brought up to 1600 K at 30 GPa at a constant heating rate of 1.0×10^6 K/s.
- 4) The system was subject to long time annealing at 1600 K and 30 GPa, up to 15 ns.
- 5) The brute-force MD faces great challenges in extending the timescale to minutes (necessary for the formation of p-D). To circumvent this discrepancy, enhanced sampling approaches must be taken. Here, to bridge the temporal gap between experiment and simulation, we enabled an adiabatic-bias molecular dynamics (ABMD) technique³⁴ to accelerate the dynamics, which was tested to be a more effective approach than other barrier-crossing techniques such as metadynamics⁶⁰ and the extended Lagrangian method⁶¹.

In the ABMD simulations stated above, a biasing potential was added to act upon a collective variable, driving the system away from the amorphous state and gearing toward the formation of paracrystallites. In this work, the mean value of the order parameter \bar{q}_6 , i.e., $\bar{q}_6^a = \Sigma_i^N \bar{q}_6^i / N$, was used as a collective variable. The parameter \bar{q}_6 for a particular atom is a coarse-grained quantity that measures the extent to which the orientation of the atoms in the coordination shells matches the orientation of the central atom, revealing the crystalline. The definition of \bar{q}_6^i is given in the following section. The biasing potential V in the ABMD simulation was constructed as:

$$V[\phi(t)] = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}K[\phi(t) - \phi_m(t)]^2 & \text{for } \phi(t) > \phi_m(t) \\ 0 & \text{for } \phi(t) \leq \phi_m(t) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $\phi(t) = [\bar{q}_6^a(t) - \bar{q}_6^t]^2$ and $\phi_m(t) = \min_{0 < \tau < t} \phi(\tau) + \eta(t)$. $\eta(t)$ is a white noise added to the minimum position of the potential. The parameters used in the bias potential were: $K = 5 \times 10^5$ eV and the target order parameter $\bar{q}_6^t = 0.6$. The ABMD method was implemented in the PLUMED package⁶².

To corroborate the classical MD results of C₆₀ collapse and polymerization during the early stage of compression, we also conducted *ab initio* MD simulation to study the phase behavior of fcc-C₆₀ (720 atoms). To this end, the fcc-C₆₀ crystal was first slowly compressed to 30 GPa by geometrical optimization. Then, the phase evolution of the compressed C₆₀ at 30 GPa from 300-1500 K was monitored by conducting *ab initio* NPT simulation at a heating rate of 2×10^{14} K/s.

Upon compression to 30 GPa at 300 K, both classical and *ab initio* MD simulations demonstrate that the C₆₀ molecules essentially maintain the cage structure but undergo significant deformations (The details can be referred to Extended Data Fig. 6). The compressed C₆₀ molecules are inter-connected by *sp*³ bonding (the fraction of *sp*³ bonds is up to ~15% at 30 GPa) (Extended Data Fig. 6a). This finding is consistent with our experimental results, where the *in situ* Raman spectra of C₆₀ indicate that the polymerization and deformation of C₆₀ molecules under compression (up to ~32 GPa) (Extended Data Fig. 6b). With increasing temperature, temperature-induced *sp*²-*sp*³ transition (25% to 70%) mainly occurs between 500 and 1200 K (Extended Data Figs. 7a and 8). There is a percolation transition of *sp*³ bonds at 500-800 K, which corresponds to the polymerization of C₆₀ molecules. Hence, from materials synthesis point of view, a hybrid *sp*²-*sp*³ type of amorphous carbon with a controllable fraction of mixed *sp*²/*sp*³ bonding can be obtained by heating to different temperatures (most preferably, above 800 K after the percolation transition takes place). Upon heating to 1600 K, the proportion of *sp*³ bonds exceeds 93%. Note that the *sp*³ fraction was estimated based on the number of four-fold bonded carbon atoms (*i.e.*, CN = 4) within a cutoff distance of 1.85 Å. This value may be slightly underestimated in comparison to that analyzed with the maximally localized Wannier function (MLWF)⁹. The structural transition of fcc-C₆₀ under 30 GPa is confirmed by *ab initio* MD simulation (Extended Data Fig. 7b).

Isothermal annealing at high temperatures (e.g., 1600 K) further promotes the *sp*²-*sp*³ transition (Extended Data Fig. 7a). The existence of parallel *sp*³ bonds, due to inter-buckyball connections in the early stage of polymerization (identifiable in Extended Data Fig. 6), persists into the a-D annealed at high temperatures. To illustrate this, we calculate the bond-orientation function of the a-D obtained at 1600 K, defined as $\Phi(\hat{r}) = \langle \delta(\frac{\mathbf{r}_{ij}}{|\mathbf{r}_{ij}|} - \hat{r}) \rangle$, where \hat{r} is a unit vector with a random orientation, \mathbf{r}_{ij} refers to an atomic bond between atom *i* and its nearest neighbor *j*, and the angular bracket refers to ensemble average. If all atomic bonds in the system are randomly distributed, one would expect a uniform distribution of $\Phi(\hat{r})$ at all directions. Nonetheless, in compressed C₆₀, despite the seemingly amorphous feature, the *sp*³ bonds in the a-D have preferred orientations, manifested by the 3D bond-orientation distribution plot and the 2-D pole figure (Extended Data Fig. 9). The *sp*³ bonds with orientational order in a-D provide fertile sites for nucleation and contribute to the nucleation of p-D during isothermal annealing.

Extending the isothermal annealing time up to 15 ns at 1600 K and 30 GPa, our classical MD simulation reveals the gradual transition from a-D to p-D via the nucleation and growth mechanism. As shown in Extended Data Fig. 10 and Supplementary Video, the fraction of CD and HD-like paracrystallites gradually increases with prolonged simulation time. Extended Data Fig. 10p and Supplementary Video show the three-dimensional (3D) structural model of

a p-D with a moderate fraction of paracrystallites (20%) achieved through classical MD. The trajectories of the paracrystallites are illustrated in Extended Data Fig. 10. To further increase the volume fraction of p-D, we resorted to adiabatic-bias molecular dynamics and the final results are presented in Fig. 3 of the main text. Note that the appearance of the paracrystallites is dynamically changing, from which one can estimate the critical nucleus size of the paracrystallites (see also Supplementary Video).

The critical nuclei are found contain approximately 20-30 atoms (~ 3.0 Å), suggesting that the paracrystallites belong to supercritical nuclei. Thermodynamically, these supercritical nuclei have certain probabilities of transitioning back to the amorphous state. Owing to the dynamic fluctuations, the maximum amount of paracrystallites is theoretically limited within a certain fraction (i.e., $\phi = 0.7$).

Structural model of NPD

Classical MD was used to generate atomic structures of NPD. To construct the initial structure, the Voronoi tessellation method was used to generate nearly-equal-sized nanograins with desirable grain sizes (1.2-2.4 nm). The grains were filled with carbon atoms in diamond cubic arrangements. The as-constructed samples, typically consisting of $\sim 100,000$ atoms, were thermally annealed at 1600 K and 30 GPa for 0.2 ns, followed by relaxations to ambient conditions at 300K and 0 GPa. The exact grain size of the NPD was computed post-mortem, based on:

$$d = \sqrt[3]{\frac{6 N \cdot \phi}{\pi n_g}} \quad (4)$$

where N is the total number of atoms, ϕ fraction of atoms associated with nanocrystals, and n_g number of grains.

Structural analysis

For short-range ordering, we proposed a local order parameter s to gauge the similarity between the first two atomic shells of each atom of a-D and that of CD or HD crystal. Inclusion of the second shell in the consideration of the local atomic environment is justified if one is to perform a Voronoi tessellation⁶³ to determine atomic coordination. The similarity order parameter s between cluster A and a reference cluster B is defined as:

$$s^B = \max_{l,\alpha,\beta,\gamma} \frac{N_B \sum_i^{N_A} \sum_j^{N_B} \exp[-(\mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{r}_i^A - \mathbf{r}_j^B)^2 / \sigma^2]}{N_A \sum_i^{N_B} \sum_j^{N_B} \exp[-(\mathbf{r}_i^B - \mathbf{r}_j^B)^2 / \sigma^2]} \quad (5)$$

where N_A and N_B denote the number of atoms in clusters A and B, respectively; \mathbf{r}_i and \mathbf{r}_j are the cartesian coordinates of the i^{th} and j^{th} atoms in the corresponding cluster; σ is a gaussian smearing parameter, which is set to 0.15 in this work; \mathbf{T} is a transformation matrix that accounts

for affine scaling transformation and cluster rotation, where l is a scaling parameter and α, β, γ are Euler angles for rotation. Having obtained s^{CD} and s^{HD} , we define $s = \max(s^{\text{CD}}, s^{\text{HD}})$. Based on the above definition, s lies between 0 and 1 (e.g., two identical clusters would yield $s = 1$ regardless of their respective orientations). A large s value implies a high similarity between the local cluster and the reference crystal, *i.e.*, enhanced short-range ordering. The similarity order parameter also provides a facile tool to quantify lattice distortions of the paracrystallites.

For medium-range ordering, a local Steinhardt order parameter \bar{q}_6 was used to evaluate the orientational order associated with each atom, which contains ordering information including a few atomic shells. For atom i , the order parameter \bar{q}_6^i was computed by:

$$\bar{q}_6^i = \frac{\sum_j^{N_c} \sum_{m=-6}^6 q_{6m}^*(i) q_{6m}(j)}{\sum_{m=-6}^6 q_{6m}^*(i) q_{6m}(i)} \quad (6)$$

where N_c is the total number of atoms included in the coordination shells (*i.e.*, medium-range clusters, typically up to 4 atomic shells in this work), and $q_{6m}(i)$ is the Steinhardt vector⁶⁴ of atom i , calculated from:

$$q_{6m}(i) = \frac{\sum_k^{CN} Y_{6m}(r_{ik})}{\sum_k^{CN} |Y_{6m}(r_{ik})|} \quad (7)$$

where k loops over all atoms in the nearest neighbors of atom i (in this work, CN = 4), and Y_{6m} is one of the sixth order spherical harmonics.

While the order parameter \bar{q}_6 yields information about the degree of structural ordering in the system, it is incapable of revealing the exact type of atomic packing (e.g., CD vs. HD). To mitigate this insufficiency, the CNA method was adopted⁶⁵. The second-nearest-neighbors of each atom in cubic diamond have fcc packing with CNA-index (421), whereas for hexagonal diamond, the 12 second-nearest-neighbors are arranged in hcp packing which can be differentiated with CNA-index (422) (see Extended Data Fig. 5). By performing CNA analysis, each atom can thus be exclusively labeled as the CD-like, HD-like, or disordered type.

Having determined the packing type of the atoms, we used the following algorithm to compute the volume fraction of the paracrystallites in the sample ϕ . Firstly, all atoms identified to have CD- or HD- like packing via CNA analysis, together with their 16 nearest neighbors, are considered as paracrystalline atoms. Secondly, other four-fold coordinated atoms that are directly bonded to the aforementioned paracrystalline atoms are included in the calculation of ϕ , to account for the ‘‘boundary’’ portion of the paracrystallites. Following this algorithm, we computed the volume fraction of the crystalline component of NPD ($d = 1.56$ nm) to be 94% for benchmarking.

To mathematically quantify the spatial extension of the paracrystallites, we invoked a two-point orientational correlation function (OCF), $\kappa(r)$, given by:

$$\kappa(r) = \left\langle \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{m=-6}^6 q_{6m}(i) \cdot q_{6m}^*(j)}{|\sum_{m=-6}^6 q_{6m}(i)| \cdot |\sum_{m=-6}^6 q_{6m}(j)|}} \delta(r_{ij} - r) \right\rangle \quad (8)$$

where the bracket indicates the calculation is averaged over all atomic pairs. The $\kappa(r)$ essentially measures the orientation relationship of two coordination polyhedra at a distance r . In two limiting cases, $\kappa(r) = 1$ for perfect crystals, and $\kappa(r) = 0$ for totally uncorrelated structures. Empirically, we consider $\kappa(r) = 0.3$ as the threshold to estimate the correlation length of the paracrystallites.

Structure factor calculation

Our *ab initio* modeling provides a reliable and predictive structural model for a-D. Nonetheless, the simulated sample has a finite size effect. If $S(Q)$ is calculated based on the Fourier transformation of the pair distribution function $g(r)$, truncation ripples will be inevitably incurred in the calculated $S(Q)$. To circumvent this issue, we accurately calculated the structure factors based on the Ornstein-Zernike (OZ) theory³⁵, which relies on solving for short-ranged direction correlation function $c(r)$ from the OZ equation:

$$h(r) = c(r) + \int dr h(r)c(r) \quad (9)$$

where $h(r) = g(r) - 1$.

In practice, we followed Baxter's factorization⁶⁶ method together with Dixon-Hutchinson's numerical algorithm⁶⁷ to obtain $c(r)$ from $g(r)$. Having derived $c(r)$, $S(Q)$ was computed from its Fourier transform $C(Q)$ following:

$$S(Q) = \frac{1}{1 - \rho C(Q)} \quad (10)$$

In this way, we were able to accurately analyze the differences between the structure factors of a-D and p-D without being encumbered by artifacts due to the finite size effect.

HRTEM simulation

HRTEM image simulations were performed based on a multi-slice algorithm as implemented in MULTEM⁶⁸. The sample thickness was typically 80 Å, and a partial coherence illumination mode was used.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding authors upon request.

Code availability

The software used for data analysis is available from H.S. upon request.

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Legends:

Fig. 1 Synthesizing fully sp^3 -bonded carbon samples at 30 GPa and 1200–1600 K for 10 min. **a**, XRD patterns indicate direct synthesis of disordered carbon from C_{60} under 30 GPa. With increasing temperature, the first main diffraction peak shifts from 2.89 to 2.95 \AA^{-1} , suggesting an increased density at higher temperatures. Inset: a typical optical photograph of the transparent bulk sample (~ 1 mm in diameter) obtained at 30 GPa and 1600 K. **b**, XRD pattern of the C_{60} precursor ($Fm\bar{3}m$). Inset: Corresponding HRTEM image and selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern. **c**, Visible Raman (Wavelength of 532 nm) spectra of samples recovered from different temperatures. The samples annealed at 1200 K and 1400 K have similar Raman features with the DLC films having a high sp^3 fraction²⁷, suggesting a trace amount of sp^2 carbon remaining in these samples. **d**, EELS spectra of samples recovered from different temperatures and cubic diamond crystal. The features at 285 and 292 eV are due to transitions of 1s electron to π^* and σ^* , corresponding to sp^2 and sp^3 bonding, respectively. The 1400 K sample has a residual 5.2% of sp^2 bonds, analyzed from the ratio of π^* and σ^* features using single-crystal graphite for calibration²⁸.

Fig. 2 TEM characterization of samples recovered from 30 GPa and 1200-1600 K. **a-b, c-d, and e-f**, Typical HRTEM images of samples and the corresponding inverse FFT images, respectively. Insets: FFT patterns corresponding to the white boxes ($7.0 \times 7.0 \text{ nm}^2$) in **(a)**, **(c)**, and **(e)**, respectively. The cyan and red circles in **(d)** and **(f)** indicate crystal-like MRO clusters. Note that the circles only serve as a guide for the eye. MRO clusters are discernable in **(f)**, where the lattice fringes marked by the cyan and red solid lines match CD- and HD-like (111) and (100) crystal planes, respectively. **g-h**, FFT patterns, corresponding to the red and cyan boxes ($2.0 \times 2.0 \text{ nm}^2$) in **(f)**, respectively. The brighter spots on the diffuse halos indicated by the colored arrows confirm the existence of CD and HD-like MRO clusters illustrated in **(f)**.

Fig. 3 Identification of p-D. **a**, Simulated structure factor $S(Q)$ of a-D and p-D ($\phi = 70\%$). **b**, Top: Experimental $S(Q)$ of the recovered samples. Bottom: Simulated $S(Q)$ of p-D with 50% paracrystallites in comparison to the experimental data. **c**, Intensity ratio of the first peak ($\sim 2.9 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$) to the second peak ($\sim 5.4 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$) as a function of volume percentage of paracrystallites. **d**, Structural model of p-D with 70% paracrystallites from MD simulation. Colors represent different types of atomic packing. Based on CNA analysis, the turquoise, gold, and red atoms represent CD-, HD-like, and disordered atomic packing within two atomic shells, respectively. The typical size and atomic arrangement of the paracrystallites are illustrated in the circles on the left. The volume ratio between CD- and HD-paracrystallites is roughly 1.5:1. **e**, Simulated HRTEM image from the paracrystalline model presented in **(d)**. The cyan and yellow circles indicate CD and HD-like clusters, respectively, in agreement with the experimental HRTEM image shown in **Fig. 2f**.

Fig. 4 Distinguishing p-D from a-D. **a**, Atomic structure of p-D vs. a-D, visualized based on their respective degree of MRO represented by the CNA index and orientational order parameter \bar{q}_6 . For a-D, the images present monotonous colors (red and blue), indicating the absence of crystal-like MRO clusters. In contrast, high-fraction MRO CD and HD-like clusters populate and become the main feature in p-D. **b**, The radial distribution function $g(r)$ (top) and orientational correlation function $\kappa(r)$ (bottom) of p-D and a-D, respectively.

Extended Data Fig. 1 XRD patterns, Raman spectra, fluorescence spectra, and EELS in the low-loss region of the recovered samples. **a**, XRD patterns of samples synthesized from different precursors: C₆₀ (top), type-1 glassy carbon (middle), and carbon onion (bottom) at 30 GPa and 1400-1800 K, respectively. At 1800 K, the appearance of weak Bragg diffraction peaks indicates nano-crystallization in the non-crystalline diamond formed from C₆₀. At 1600 K, fully sp^3 -bonded p-D was identified. By contrast, in cases of using type-1 glassy carbon and carbon onion as the starting material, crystallization precedes the complete conversion of sp^2 to sp^3 carbon at 30 GPa and 1400-1600 K, preempting the formation of fully sp^3 -bonded paracrystalline diamond. The experiments demonstrate the importance of the structure of the starting material in the formation pathway of p-D. **b**, Visible Raman (532 nm) spectrum of the sample recovered at 30 GPa and 1400 K, with background removed. The broadened Raman peak can be fit with a *D* peak at 1378 cm⁻¹ and a *G* peak at 1556 cm⁻¹. The peak intensity ratio of I_D/I_G is 0.66 and the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the *G* peak is 175 cm⁻¹. Similar to our work, the presence of sp^2 bonds results in a wide Raman peak between 1400 cm⁻¹ and 1700 cm⁻¹ in the visible Raman spectra of diamond-like carbon (DLC) films²⁷. **c**, Ultraviolet (UV) Raman spectra of the samples recovered from 1400 and 1500 K, respectively. The strong peak at 1110 cm⁻¹ in the UV Raman spectrum of the sample recovered at 30 GPa and 1400 K is attributed to the *T* peak caused by sp^3 bonds²⁷. Fitting the Raman profile yields a peak intensity ratio of I_T/I_G 0.91, which is higher than that of DLC films with 88% sp^3 bonds, indicating a higher concentration of sp^3 bonds in the sample²⁷. On the other hand, for the sample recovered from 1500 K, no obvious peaks are discernible in the UV Raman spectrum, indicating the absence of sp^2 bonds in the as-synthesized disordered carbon⁸. **d**, Fluorescence spectra (excitation wavelength of 532 nm) of the sample from 1600 K and type Ia diamond. A main fluorescence peak centered around 702 nm suggests the high background in the Raman spectra is due to a fluorescence effect. **e**, EELS in the low-loss region of diamond crystal, single-crystal graphite, and samples synthesized from C₆₀ under 30 GPa and 1400-1500 K. Based on plasmon peak energy derived from low-loss EELS²⁸, the densities of the recovered samples at 1400-1600 K were calculated to be 3.11, 3.20, and 3.25 g/cm³, respectively. Due to the presence of ~5.2% sp^2 carbon, the sample recovered from 1400 K has a lower density of 3.11 g/cm³.

Extended Data Fig. 2 HRTEM images of samples recovered at 30 GPa and different

temperatures. a-c, Typical HRTEM images of samples synthesized at 30 GPa and 1500, 1600, and 1800 K, respectively. **a-c and h-j,** The inverse FFT images and FFT patterns corresponding to the areas marked by the white boxes ($7.0 \times 7.0 \text{ nm}^2$) in **(a)**, **(b)**, and **(c)**, respectively. The cyan and yellow circles in **(e and f)** indicate cubic- and hexagonal-like MRO clusters, respectively. In subfigure **g**, the lattice fringes marked with cyan and yellow solid lines indicate that nanosized cubic and hexagonal diamond crystallites are precipitated from the non-crystalline matrix at 1800 K.

Extended Data Fig. 3 Structure factor $S(Q)$, structural models, and simulated HRTEM images of simulated a-D, p-D with different fractions of paracrystallites, and NPD with different grain sizes. **a,** $S(Q)$ of simulated a-D and p-D with different fractions of paracrystallites. With increasing ϕ , the intensity of the first peak increases, and the position of the peak shifts to high-Q, which is consistent with the experimental observation that at higher annealing temperatures, the intensity of the first peak increases and the position moves to the right (from 2.89 \AA^{-1} at 1200 K to 2.95 \AA^{-1} at 1600 K, Fig. 3b in the main text). **b,** $S(Q)$ of simulated NPDs with different grain sizes, juxtaposed with that of the 1800 K sample from our experiment. For the simulated NPD samples, the peak intensity decreases and the peak width broadens as the grain size is refined. Bragg peaks are clearly discernable for the samples with a grain size of 1.2 nm. Experimentally, the protruding diffraction peaks in the 1800 K sample corresponds exactly to the characteristic Bragg peaks of NPD, indicative of crystallization. **c,** In ultrafine NPD, the less-distorted “core” regions of the nanocrystals (blue spheres) are clearly seen. For NPD with $d = 1.56 \text{ nm}$, ϕ is estimated to be 94%, meaning 6% atoms are located at the interfaces and cannot be properly assigned to any of the crystalline grains.

Extended Data Fig. 4 Short-range ordering of a-D, a-Si, p-D, and NPD. **a,** Distributions of tetrahedrality q_t for a-D and a-Si, both of which were obtained from the WWW bond-switching approach and further relaxed with *ab initio* MD. The tetrahedral order parameter q_t is defined as $q_t = 1 - \frac{3}{8} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=i+1}^4 (\cos \theta_{ij} + 1/3)^2$, where θ_{ij} is the angle formed by two vectors pointing from the center silicon to two of its neighboring silicon atoms. The summation runs over all the combinations of the four nearest neighbors. The narrow distribution of a-D clearly indicates that a-D has a strong tetrahedral SRO than a-Si. **b,** Bond-angle distribution within the first atomic shell for a-D and a-Si. Compared with a-Si, a-D has a narrower bond-angle distribution. **c,** Distributions of the 2nd-nearest-neighbor order parameter s of a-D and a-Si. The order parameter s measures the similarity of the local atomic environment (16 atoms) of a central atom with respect to perfect CD or HD lattice arrangements. The higher the s value, the less distortion of the local cluster. Compared with a-Si, the distribution function of s for a-D shifts to high s values with a centroid of 0.42, suggesting much enhanced SRO within the first two atomic shells in a-D. The high similarity of the local atomic environments between a-D

and crystalline diamond stems from the strong directional sp^3 bonding of carbon, as evidenced from the narrower bond-angle distribution of a-D in comparison to that of a-Si. **d**, Distributions s of a-D, p-D, and NPD with a grain size of 1.92 nm. The inset atomic clusters illustrate the cluster configurations (red spheres) corresponding to their degree of similarity with the perfect CD lattice arrangement (green spheres). Paracrystalline diamond has a medium s value (0.51) between that of a-D and NPD, revealing crystalline ordering in p-D. It is worth noting that, for NPD with $d = 1.92$ nm, the distribution spike at $s = 0.96$ corresponds to interior atoms in nano-grains that are less distorted. Such atoms are absent in paracrystalline diamond, marking the distinction between p-D and NPD.

Extended Data Fig. 5 Two atomic-shell structures (side and top views) of CD and HD (16 nearest neighbors) atomic packing. The 12 second nearest neighbors in CD and HD are arranged in the FCC and HCP packing modes, respectively.

Extended Data Fig. 6 Structural evolution of C_{60} under room-temperature compression. **a**, Structure model (Only one layer is shown) of C_{60} under 30 GPa and room temperature (300 K), obtained by classic and *ab initio* MD. Under high pressure (30 GPa), the inter-molecule distance reduces to 0.86 or 0.87 nm from 1.0 nm. During compression to 30 GPa at room temperature, the buckyballs are deformed and inter-buckyball bonding occurs by formation of four-fold (sp^3) bonds (15%). In this and the following figures, the atoms with sp^3 bonding are colored in blue. The fraction of sp^3 atoms was approximated by the number of 4-fold coordinated atoms within a cut off distance (in this work, $r_{cut} = 1.85$ Å). We shall point out that, the sp^3 fraction calculated this way is slightly underestimated in comparison to that calculated quantum-mechanically, e.g., with the maximally localized Wannier function (MLWF). **b**, *In situ* Raman spectra of C_{60} under compression (up to ~ 32 GPa) without pressure transmitting medium, with an excitation wavelength of 532 nm. With increasing pressure, the Raman peaks of the A_g mode corresponding to the breathing of totally symmetric vibrations and the H_g mode are gradually broadened with decreased intensity, suggesting a gradual decline of the symmetric environment of pristine C_{60} , associated with the polymerization of buckyballs⁶⁹ and the formation of sp^3 bonds⁷⁰, consistent with our theoretical results.

Extended Data Fig. 7 MD simulation of fcc- C_{60} heated to different temperatures at 30 GPa. **a**, Classic MD simulation of fcc- C_{60} , heating rate: 10^{10} K/s. The fraction of sp^3 bonds increase with increasing temperature. There is a percolation transition of sp^3 bonds at 500-800 K. Such a percolation transition corresponds to the polymerization of C_{60} molecules. It should be pointed out that the fractions of sp^3 bonding were determined based on the criterion of 4-fold bonding within 1.85 Å, which may slightly underestimate the real sp^3 fraction of the sample by a few percent. **b**, *Ab initio* MD simulation of fcc- C_{60} (720 atoms), heating rate: 2×10^{14} K/s. Similar to classic MD simulation, the fraction of sp^3 bonds increases with increasing temperature in *ab initio* MD. The simulation results validate what was observed in classical

MD. Note the persistence of parallel sp^3 bonds at 900 K and 1200 K.

Extended Data Fig. 8 Enthalpy and volume as a function of temperature during the heating treatment of C₆₀ at 30 GPa. The decrease of enthalpy with increasing temperature (500-1250 K) indicates the main sp^2 - sp^3 transition (25% to 70% as shown in Extended Data Fig. 7a) occurs between 500 K and 1250 K, accompanied by the densification of the material due to the formation of sp^3 bonding. The uprise of the enthalpy at temperatures below 500 K and above 1250 K is mainly due to the thermal effect.

Extended Data Fig. 9 Hidden orientational ordering of sp^3 bonds in compressed C₆₀. Top: Structure model of a-D obtained from C₆₀ after 30 GPa and 1600 K without long-time isothermal annealing (Extended Data Fig. 7a). Middle: 3D bond-orientation distribution function projected onto the unit sphere surface. Bottom: Two-dimensional stereographic projection of the bond-orientation function showing the pole figure of preferred bond orientations. The lines serve as a guide to the eye. Heterogeneous intensity distributions suggest that the sp^3 bonds in the as-obtained a-D have preferred orientations, inherited from the initial parallel sp^3 bonds in the early stage of polymerization.

Extended Data Fig. 10 Classic MD simulation of the structural evolution of a-D during isothermal annealing at 1600 K and 30 GPa, 6400 atoms, up to 15 ns. Only the core atoms of the paracrystallites are shown. The paracrystallites marked by turquoise and gold have CD and HD-like structures, respectively. The fraction of paracrystallites increases with the annealing time (**a-o**, at a time interval of 1 ns per image). The last image (**p**) shows a 3D configuration paracrystalline diamond with $\phi = 20\%$ obtained from brute-force classical MD. To further increase the volume fraction of p-D, we resorted to adiabatic-bias molecular dynamics and the final results are given in Fig. 3 of the main text. See Supplementary Video for the fluctuations of the paracrystallites.

Extended Data Fig. 11 Mechanical properties of recovered samples. **a**, Vickers hardness H_v and fracture toughness K_{IC} of the samples recovered at 30 GPa and different temperatures, measured at 4.9 and 9.8 N, respectively. Inset: an optical image of the indentation of p-D recovered from 1600 K. **b**, Side-by-side comparison of the loading/unloading displacement curves of p-D recovered from 1600 K and natural diamond in the nanoindentation experiment. Inset: A table of nanoindentation hardness H_N and elastic modulus E obtained from different test points. **c**, Overview of shear modulus G versus Vickers hardness H_v for typical superhard ceramics^{42,46,71,72}. The shear modulus G (437.9 ± 4.7 GPa) and bulk modulus K (363.3 ± 3.9 GPa) was derived through formulas $G = E/[2(1+\mu)]$ and $K = E/[3(1-2\mu)]$, where the elastic modulus E (937.2 ± 10.1 GPa) was experimentally measured (shown in b) and μ is the Poisson's ratio (0.07) of diamond. **Error bars in a and c indicate the standard deviations.** **d**, Summary for the calculated and experimental hardness of typical sp^3 carbons of p-D, diamond^{42,46}, hexagonal

diamond⁷³, carbon clathrates⁷⁴, NPD^{39,41} and nanotwinned diamond (NTD)^{41,75}. **e**, Comparison of theoretical Young's modulus and bulk modulus of p-D and diamond⁷⁶. For the *ab initio* calculations, we used DFT-based *ab initio* modeling stated in the Methods section but with a smaller-sized p-D sample (240 atoms) derived from classical MD.

Extended Data Fig. 12 Thermostability of p-D. **a**, Both thermogravimetry (TG) and DSC curves of p-D were measured in air at a heating rate of 5 K/min. **b**, Thermostability of p-D, compared with other superhard carbons⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹. Superhard (50-80 GPa) DLC films have a wide range of onset oxidation temperature (673-873 K), depending on the fraction of *sp*³ bonds. The thermostability of p-D is superior to that of NPD (*d* = ~13 nm)⁴³.